

Significance Of Surgical Site Infections Following Caesarean Section and Associated Risk Factors in A Tertiary Care Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Background: With a reported prevalence of 3–20%, surgical site infection (SSI) is one of the most frequent complications after caesarean section (CS). SSI places enormous strain on the mother and the medical system. Additionally, it has a 3% maximum rate of maternal morbidity and mortality linked to it.

Aim: To find out the prevalence of surgical site infection and associated risk factors in patients post caesarean section

Methods: An observational cross-section study among patients undergoing LSCS in Trichy SRM Medical College, Hospital

Results: The incidence of SSI was found to be 13.5% in our study

Conclusions: The risk of surgical site infection following caesarean section is increased by a number of risk factors. Therefore, in patients who have these risk factors, obstetricians should think about doing postoperative follow-ups sooner or more frequently.

Keywords: *Infection, Trichy, Risk factors, LSCS, SSI*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most common major surgical procedures in obstetrics is the caesarean section (CS). When properly recommended, it can save both the mother's and the foetus' lives and avert unfavourable obstetric outcomes¹. However, worries regarding the danger of maternal death and morbidity that goes hand in hand with the increased global rate of caesarean deliveries are becoming more prevalent^{2,3}. Postpartum endometritis, haemorrhage, pelvic organ damage, thromboembolic disorders, anaesthesia-related complications, and wound issues are among the major risks linked to caesarean delivery⁴.

A surgical site infection (SSI) is defined as an infection that develops within 30 days following surgery and affects the skin and subcutaneous tissue of the incision (superficial incisional), the deep soft tissue of the incision (deep incisional), and/or any portion of the anatomy (organs and spaces, for example) that was opened or moved during the procedure⁵. It is the most prevalent infection among surgical patients and also a significant contributor to the morbidity and death of mothers⁶.

A common consequence after caesarean section is surgical site infection, which occurs in 13.5% of cases in TSRM^{7,8}. The risk of surgical site infection following caesarean section is increased by a number of risk factors, including advanced age, obesity, maternal complications during pregnancy, labor beginning during the procedure, prolonged rupture of the membrane lasting longer than eighteen hours, and more than five PV examinations^{9,10}.

Readmission of postpartum patients to the hospital has a significant negative influence on a mother's mental health in addition to adding to the workload for the facility and medical personnel^{11,12}. Thus, it may be crucial to pinpoint SSI risk factors in a hospital context in order to lower maternal morbidity and death rates^{4,13,14}. As a result, many risk variables that may be more common in our setting were unknown to the healthcare system.

Infections connected to wounds, such as surgical site infections after caesarean sections, are a leading source of morbidity and mortality, lengthening hospital stays for patients and driving up expenses^{15,16}. The majority of surgical site infections can be avoided. Pre-, intra-, and postoperative treatment phases all offer opportunities to lower the risk of infection¹⁷.

The main objective of this study is to determine the incidence of SSI following LSCS in TSRM, classify them, and analyse different host, pregnancy, and procedure-related risk factors.

METHODS

Study Design & Area:

A prospective observational cross-sectional study was conducted among patients undergoing LSCS at Trichy SRM Medical College, Hospital for a period of 6 months from January 2024 to June 2024.

Sample size:

A sample size of 220 was taken for this study. The study participants were selected by convenient sampling technique.

Inclusion criteria:

All patients who will be undergoing caesarean sections (both elective and emergency) at Trichy SRM Medical College, Trichy, Tamil Nadu.

Exclusion criteria:

Patients who underwent caesarean section in other hospital, Patients with preexisting skin infection and Immunocompromised patients (patient on steroids, serology positive)

Study procedure:

After obtaining ethical approval from Institutional Human Ethics Committee and permission at all levels to conduct the survey, after getting informed and written consent patients undergoing LSCS (elective & emergency) will be taken for this study.

Demographic and relevant clinical data like indication of CS, previous pregnancies, duration of labour, hygiene practices of patient, PROM, GDM, PIH, intraoperative blood loss, transfusion history if present, details of antibiotic prophylaxis will be recorded.

Suture site will be evaluated from POD-3 till patient gets discharged. Details will be recorded for appearance of signs and symptoms of SSI like fever, localized pain, swelling, induration, dehiscence or purulent discharge from suture site.

Purulent discharge, if any, from the incision site will be subjected to culture and sensitivity testing before administration of antibiotics. All patients with SSI will be followed up on D3/D5 of oral/IV antibiotic for evaluation of wound status viz., discharge from wound site, wound gaping, need for daily dressing, need for secondary suturing.

Statistical Analysis:

Collected data was entered in Microsoft excel and statistical analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Descriptive statistics formed the basis of the analysis. Percentages were evaluated for the categorical variables.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows demographic characteristics of the study participants in our study. 93 (42.2%) of the participants belonged to age group of 18-25 years, 78 belonged to 25-30 years and 49 belonged to 31-35 years category. 116 (52.7%) had completed high school, 96 had completed graduate degree and 8 had completed postgraduate degree. There were no illiterates in our study. Half (51.4%) our participants had normal BMI, 30.5% were in overweight category and 18.1% were obese. Among our study participants, 126 (57.3%) were primi and 94 were multigravida. Majority of the participants (60.5%) underwent elective LSCS.

Table 2 shows the distribution of surgical site infection types. 12 (5.4%) had developed superficial surgical site infection and 18 (8.1%) had developed deep surgical site infection. The total incidence of surgical site infection from our study was 13.5%. This was relatable to a study conducted by Astha et al ¹.

Table 3 showed various indications for LSCS. 56 participants underwent LSCS for fetal distress, 78 underwent LSCS for previous LSCS, 23 underwent LSCS for placental problems like placenta previa, abruptio placentae. 18 underwent LSCS for abnormal presentations, 13 underwent LSCS for eclampsia, 15 underwent LSCS for prolonged labour and 11 underwent LSCS for multiple reasons like twins, oligohydramnios, etc.

Table 4 shows the association between various risk factors and surgical site infections. Various risk factors like age, BMI, parity, type of LSCS and various maternal complications like Gestational diabetes, PIH, Thyroid disorders were considered. A chi square test was done to find association between risk factors and SSI. A p value of <0.05 was considered significant. Among various risk factors compared, BMI, parity and pre-existing maternal complications were found to be statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

The present study was undertaken in Obstetrics Gynaecology department in Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital among patients undergoing caesarean section. This study was conducted among 220 participants. The main purpose was to find out prevalence of surgical site infection following caesarean section during postoperative period.

In the present study the total prevalence of surgical site infection was found to be 13.5%. our findings was consistent with the study conducted Mishra et al¹⁷ who conducted on total of 186 cases were studied and the incidence rate of surgical site infection was 13 (6.99%)

In our present study, we found that majority of surgical site infection was common among younger age group between 18-25 years. This was similar to the findings on study conducted by Regmi et al¹ where, the high incidence was found among mean age group of 25.88 years.

BMI, parity and type of LSCS were considered in our present study and found that women with normal BMI had high incidence of infection, primipara had more incidence of operative infection and elective LSCS had more chance of surgical site infection. This maybe attributed to lack of awareness regarding postoperative wound care. Among LSCS patients, those who were operated for previous LSCS and foetal distress had high incidence of infection. This was consistent with study conducted by Onuzo et al¹⁶ among postoperative mothers.

Interestingly education played a significant role in surgical site infection. More incidence was found among lesser educational qualification. In other words, higher the education, lesser the incidence of infection. This may be attributed to knowledge about wound care. BMI and parity were found to be closely associated with surgical infection along with maternal complication. These findings are similar to study conducted by Dutta et al¹⁴ where education and socioeconomic status were found to influence postoperative wound infection to a significant extent.

LIMITATIONS

The present study was conducted in a small town in southern part of India with limited variables. This study cannot be generalised with the general population.

CONCLUSION

In our present study, BMI, parity and maternal disorders were found significant in association of surgical site infections. Therefore, in patients who have these risk factors, obstetricians should think about doing postoperative follow-ups sooner or more frequently. In order to lower the frequency of surgical site infections after caesarean sections, obstetricians should make an effort to avoid avoidable risk factors.

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Conflict of interest: there is no conflict of interest

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REFERENCES

1. Regmi, A., Ojha, N., Singh, M., Ghimire, A. & Kharel, N. Risk Factors Associated with Surgical Site Infection following Cesarean Section in Tertiary Care Hospital, Nepal. *Int. J. Reprod. Med.* **2022**, 4442453 (2022).
2. Abdel Jalil, M. H. *et al.* Surgical site infections following caesarean operations at a Jordanian teaching hospital: Frequency and implicated factors. *Sci. Rep.* **7**, 12210 (2017).
3. Albaharnah, S. F., Rashed, S. A., Almuhaimeed, R. S. & Abohelaika, S. Incidence of Surgical Site Infection Following Cesarean Section and Its Associated Factors in a Hospital of the Eastern Region, Saudi Arabia: A Retrospective Cohort Study. *Healthcare* **12**, 1474 (2024).
4. Alnajjar, M. S. & Alashker, D. A. Surgical site infections following caesarean sections at Emirati teaching hospital: Incidence and implicated factors. *Sci. Rep.* **10**, 18702 (2020).
5. Kvalvik, S. A., Rasmussen, S., Thornhill, H. F. & Baghestan, E. Risk factors for surgical site infection following cesarean delivery: A hospital-based case–control study. *Acta Obstet. Gynecol. Scand.* **100**, 2167–2175 (2021).
6. Gomaa, K. *et al.* Incidence, risk factors and management of post cesarean section surgical site infection (SSI) in a tertiary hospital in Egypt: a five year retrospective study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* **21**, 634 (2021).
7. Zejnullahu, V. A., Isjanovska, R., Sejfiija, Z. & Zejnullahu, V. A. Surgical site infections after cesarean sections at the University Clinical Center of Kosovo: rates, microbiological profile and risk factors. *BMC Infect. Dis.* **19**, 752 (2019).
8. Odada, D., Shah, J., Mbithi, A. & Shah, R. Surgical site infections post cesarean section and associated risk factors: a retrospective case-control study at a tertiary hospital in Kenya. *Infect. Prev. Pract.* **6**, 100333 (2024).
9. Erritty, M. *et al.* Evaluation of independent risk factors associated with surgical site infections from caesarean section. *Arch. Gynecol. Obstet.* **308**, 1775–1783 (2023).
10. Farid Mojtahedi, M. *et al.* Global incidence of surgical site infections following caesarean section: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J. Hosp. Infect.* **139**, 82–92 (2023).
11. Saeed, K. B. M., Greene, R. A., Corcoran, P. & O’Neill, S. M. Incidence of surgical site infection following caesarean section: a systematic review and meta-analysis protocol. *BMJ Open* **7**, e013037 (2017).
12. Alfouzan, W., Fadhli, M. A., Abdo, N., Alali, W. & Dhar, R. Surgical site infection following cesarean section in a general hospital in Kuwait: trends and risk factors. *Epidemiol. Infect.* **147**, e287 (2019).

13. Gupta, S., Manchanda, V., Sachdev, P., Kumar Saini, R. & Joy, M. Study of incidence and risk factors of surgical site infections in lower segment caesarean section cases of tertiary care hospital of north India. *Indian J. Med. Microbiol.* **39**, 1–5 (2021).
14. Dutta, B. K., Basumatary, B. K. & Sarma, A. Surgical Site Infection Following Caesarean Section in a Tertiary Care Hospital. *J. Evid. Based Med. Healthc.* **7**, 01–05 (2020).
15. C, W. *et al.* Risk factors for surgical site infection following caesarean section in England: results from a multicentre cohort study. *BJOG Int. J. Obstet. Gynaecol.* **119**, (2012).
16. Onuzo, C. N. *et al.* Surgical site infections following caesarean sections in the largest teaching hospital in Ghana. *Infect. Prev. Pract.* **4**, 100203 (2022).
17. Mishra, R. *et al.* SURGICAL SITE INFECTION FOLLOWING CESAREAN SECTION AND ITS ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS AT A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL IN CHITWAN. *J. Chitwan Med. Coll.* **10**, 47–51 (2020).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics

Variables		Frequency (n)	%
Age	18-25 yrs	93	42.2
	25-30 yrs	78	35.5
	31-35 yrs	49	22.3
Education	High school	116	52.7
	Graduate	96	43.6
	Postgraduate	8	3.7
BMI	Normal	113	51.4
	Overweight	67	30.5
	Obesity	40	18.1
Parity	Primi	126	57.3
	Multi	94	42.7
Type of LSCS	Emergency	87	39.5
	Elective	133	60.5

Table 2. Distribution of type of SSI

TYPE	Frequency (n)	Percentage %
Superficial	12	5.4
Deep	18	8.1
Total	30	13.5

Table 3. Various indication for LSCS

Indication	(n)	%
Foetal distress	56	25.5
Previous LSCS	78	35.5
Placenta related problems	23	10.5
Abnormal presentation	18	8.2
Eclampsia	13	5.9
Cephalon-pelvic disproportion	6	2.7
Prolonged labour	15	6.8
Others	11	5

Table 4. Association between risk factors and SSI

Risk factors		SSI	X ²	Df	P value
Age	18-25 yrs	4	13.2	2	0.5
	25-30 yrs	12			
	31-35 yrs	14			
BMI	Normal	3	8.6	3	0.02
	Overweight	14			
	Obesity	13			
Parity	Primi	12	6.3	2	0.03
	Multi	18			
Type of LSCS	Emergency	19	3.6	1	0.7
	Elective	11			
Maternal complication	Yes	16	2.6	1	<0.01
	No	14			